

A utility-oriented framework towards an Energy -as-a-Service model transformation

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Abstract

There is clear evidence that Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) can play a critical role in enabling consumer active participation in future Internet of Grid business models - through technology assisted behavioural change. Several experiments and studies conducted around the globe, have concluded that consumer feedback (especially personalized and human-centric) supported by sophisticated ICT applications and intelligent controls can effectively alter consumer behaviour and empower them to achieve significant benefits through energy and cost savings (smartEN, 2020). Towards this direction, we present in this paper an innovative energy management framework for residential and tertiary buildings focusing on the identification of the energy-hungry behaviours for building further aiming to trigger appropriate energy-use feedback to occupants and engage them into a continuous behavioural based energy efficiency framework. The proposed energy management framework is validated in real-life conditions by a large population of residential and commercial consumers in five dispersed geographical areas and the early results are presented in this paper. In addition, the evaluation of innovative business plans is examined in this paper.

Keywords: Behavioral change, energy transformation

1. A Service oriented energy management framework

At first, the details of the innovative retailer-oriented energy change framework are presented with the focus on the quantification and revelation of energy-savvy customers on the way to convey meaningful real time energy-use feedback and engage them into a continuous process of learning and improvement. The overall behavioural based personalized energy efficiency framework is further complemented with a light-weight, human-centric, control framework so as to minimize energy waste, but fully preserving occupants comfort boundaries into indoor environmental conditions. On the way to ensure accuracy and reliability on the provision of energy management services, we adopt the Internet of Things/Services principles to set the first and backbone data layer of the

proposed framework; responsible to collect all necessary information required for the analysis. Live information streams captured from low-cost off-the-shelf smart devices spanning from smart meters, sensors deployed for monitoring ambient/ hygienic conditions and smart controllers, are continuously processed and further incorporated in a semantically unified **Sensing and Data Management Layer** (UtilitEE Project – D3.1). This data management layer establishes an easy to deploy, flexible & scalable middleware layer to enable secure integration with a diverse typology of building networks and also integrate data from external sources (weather data, energy pricing data, consumer

demographics); data to be further utilized by several energy business applications.

The **Internal Core Services layer** stand as the knowledge intensive layer of the system towards the extraction of information from the raw data. Different types of applications are designed and developed following a microservices based approach. The **Context Aware Profiling** layer comprises the heart of the System and includes readings from sensing and energy measurement data to transform raw energy data into accurate, intuitive and context-aware Behavioural Profiles. These enhanced and integrated profiles incorporate all personalized and contextual (environmental, temporal) aspects of (energy related) behaviour, dynamically constructed and continuously updated based on real-time data streams from the installations available in end customers premises. The **Baseline and Energy Waste Layer** in parallel to the Context Aware Profiling layer generates objective and normalized energy baselines taking into account socio-demographic and building operational characteristics as well as energy related data to apply International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol (IPMVP) based normalization methodologies. The definition of accurate energy baselines that incorporate building operational aspects can be further analyzed to reveal major energy related patterns (most often of habitual and

unconscious nature) and allow for systematic classification of consumers into clusters of consistent behaviour as well as the formulation of norms - behavioural profile patterns that can be used as points of reference for specific user groups. Such consumer clusters stand as the basis for the automatic detection of energy waste outliers; deviations from baseline/typical operation. The extraction of normative and outlier values may be considered as useful knowledge for the definition of personalized energy efficiency guidance and recommendation. Last but not least, the **disaggregation layer** acts as a complement analytics layer to allow whole energy consumption data distinction to separate building appliances. By decomposing the energy consumption profile, it is possible to extract specific information about the use of individual appliances, information which is more useful for the customers than reporting the total electricity usage by using a single sensor for the entire zone. The energy footprint of specific devices will then enable the creation of bespoke behavioural profiles that may be considered as reference point for further analysis.

The End User Application layer stand as the business application layer of the holistic framework, setting a pool of business applications for the end users, targeting mainly the customers of the utilities but providing also energy services to the retailer stakeholders.

Figure 1: A retailer-oriented energy change framework.

Following the microservices concept adopted in the overall architecture, a non-exhaustive list of energy apps is delivered, fully exploiting the raw data and the knowledge extracted from the aforementioned pillars. The enriched visualization and recommendations layer is the main customers' application towards the enriched visualization of personalized information. The **Systemic and Enhanced Building Performance Rating** establishes a robust framework of energy performance indicators on various spatio-temporal levels and a macroscopic and systemic view on building energy performance. The normalization process adopted on **Enhanced Display Energy Certificate (eDECs)** visualization mitigates asymmetries caused by different building characteristics (envelope, insulation, window types), or climate/micro-climate conditions and occupancy, ensuring that way a fair performance benchmarking among consumers with similar behaviours and characteristics. The eDECs as the focal visualization layer constitute also the point of reference and interaction with individual consumers as part of the behavioural engagement process; by allowing energy consumers to understand their energy waste sources, compare themselves against peers and ultimately, receive appropriate, personalized and tailor-made feedback and guidance towards improving their overall energy performance.

The **Activity Clock** is a view of the system focusing mainly on residential customers to provide the user with a visual feedback on their energy consumption and overall performance (on the basis of the Systemic & Enhanced Building Performance Rating Layer and the associated Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)). The association of consumption patterns with daily activities and profiles is a main feature of the application. The Activity Dashboard on the other hand is defined as the view of the system for tertiary buildings and users including peer performance views and insight about detailed energy use down to appliance level.

The human centric automation and remote-control layer incorporates two distinct services. Based on the Context-Aware Profiles, the **Human-Centric Automation** Module intelligently adjusts lights and Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) set points according to individual consumer comfort preferences and on the way to conserve

energy. To further ensure compliance of control with end customer's needs, automated actions are followed by discrete notifications informing them about the alteration in lights or HVAC operation and the benefits of the corrective control actions. On the other hand, the **remote control and scheduling application** complement the recommendation process and enable consumers to remotely accept and authorize automatic, recommended energy efficiency preserving actions or operational schedules for individual appliances and equipment through intuitive user interfaces focusing on eliminating energy waste and improving energy footprint.

Along with the applications for the end customers, business applications for the retailer stakeholders are developed. The **Pilot Site Monitoring Application** offers a variety of services to the utilities addressing their needs for the continuous analysis of consumer behavioural dynamics and further the coordination of the behavioural change services through the configuration, planning and roll-out of efficient behavioural change strategies on the basis of the business models of the utilities. Related to the latter, the scope of the application is twofold: to first enable the utilities to set their parameters associated with their business domain and perspective and further to ensure that continuous impact & performance evaluation of the different strategies is performed as well as necessary re-design and corrective actions in order to meet the goals as set by the actors of the tool.

We presented above the different layers of the holistic energy management framework as an ICT application focusing on the provision of energy analytics and business applications to the retailer stakeholders. Special focus is delivered on the different business applications and services developed in the context of knowledge extracted from the raw data and in line with the business models of interest for the utilities. This is a focal point for the proposed framework as the key objective is to provide energy business applications to meet practical needs and emerging demands of the radically transforming energy utilities. Some key points of the different business applications and the linkage to the different business models is presented in the following section.

2. Behaviour driven energy business applications

Along with the presentation of the whole picture for the ICT driven energy management framework, details and insights about the usability of the key business applications is delivered in this section. The business perspective of the proposed framework is presented as a circular process, where the business needs trigger the design and functionality of the energy apps, while the results from the demonstration of the services trigger utilities to reform their traditional business models on the way to refine new and more focused business concepts. The business-centric approach as considered for the design of the platform is presented in the following schema (UtilitEE Project – D1.2).

As an anchor point of the overall concept is the identification of new business needs from the utilities. As stated above, there is an emerging need for traditional utilities to transform their business operations and start providing new products and energy services to their customers. New service-oriented business model should build upon their baseline offering including energy use analytics and tailor-made guidance for improving energy behaviours and overall energy and cost performance. The emerging concepts of “Utility as an Energy Service Company (ESCO)” that allows utilities

to balance and hedge losses from energy savings (reduced energy sales) through a novel energy efficiency services concept and “Utility as Aggregator” model which enables retailers/utilities to counterbalance losses from energy savings (less energy sold) by bidding consumer flexibility in energy markets (through accumulation/aggregation of their clientele’s demand flexibility) is a starting point for the work.

More specifically, business models in the field of energy services focus mainly on the increased Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) and the associated certificates or towards the provision of comfort preserving home automation services. On the other hand, the participation in flexibility services seems more profitable for the utilities with demand side management focusing on: (a) Distribution System Operator (DSO) costs minimization by eliminating the network costs of the energy bill (b) community Virtual Power Plant (VPPs) in order to perform changes in the consumption patterns according on what market is going to be traded the aggregated flexibility through a real-time remote load control. (c) dynamic retailer pricing based on regulation forcing for dynamic pricing. (d) supply/demand imbalance management on the way to increase self-consumption at local level and thus ensure the active transformation of consumers to prosumer

Figure 2: A business-centric approach for the energy as a service framework.

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Add Campaign". It contains the following fields and controls:

- Business Strategy Name:** A text input field with a character count of "0 / 64".
- Business Strategy Type:** A dropdown menu.
- Priority:** A dropdown menu.
- Portfolio Assets:** A dropdown menu.
- Consumption Reduction (%):** A slider control.
- Max number of notifications / week:** A slider control with the value "1" displayed.
- Start Date:** A date picker showing "2019-10-24".
- Start Time:** A time picker showing "00:00".
- End Date:** A date picker showing "2019-10-24".
- End Time:** A time picker showing "23:59".
- Buttons:** "CLOSE" and "ADD" buttons are located at the bottom right of the form.

Figure 3: A business strategies settings viewpoint.

The next step of the holistic business concept is the transformation of the business needs to operational strategies. The business models as high-level objectives can be further translated into operational settings, either associated with long term demand shed strategies where the focus is on energy efficiency or short-term demand shifting strategies towards addressing the dynamic volatility on energy and ancillary services markets. By combining short term automation with long term end user's engagement, the proposed framework targets to achieve significant energy savings while enabling their participation in innovative demand response schemas. The key model parameters for the portfolio strategies are related to the start and end date of each business strategy, the time schedule, the associated location, the goal target and the severity of each business campaign. The retailers should be able to accordingly set or modify the respective parameters required for the business context of their operation. For that reason, a dedicated view of the pilot site monitoring application is available to set dynamically the constraints of the operational framework.

By defining the respective parameters, an optimization process is performed towards allocating personalized strategies to the customers that consist of the selected portfolio. The selection is performed taking into account building energy related parameters (e.g. baseline and waste outliers) and the segmentation of their portfolio to the different clusters (norms- three different clusters are defined). Following this high-level segmentation, the appropriate triggering messages are delivered to the customers applications. The delivery of the personalized messages is following a user oriented behavioural segmentation methodology that has been adopted in the holistic framework.; a bottom up approach where the different customers are clustered to specific groups based on their inherent characteristics (e.g. interest to participate, focus on cost/energy/environmental conditions etc...). Along with the customers classification to the different groups, additional parameters like the timeframe for the different campaigns, waste outlier's detection etc... are considered in the holistic behavioural based triggering framework (UtilitEE Project – D1.4) as depicted in the figure 3.

The guidance framework is further complemented by intuitive applications for the utility customers. Through the activity clock, the customers may get a quick but comprehensive snapshot of their daily activities, breaking down the day into activity-filled timeslots and revealing their impact on overall energy footprint using color-coding to highlight the energy hungry activities. Direct, personalized, normative and comparative feedback at individual level is available to the residential customers. On the other hand, the Activity Dashboard is defined as an extension of the Activity Clock to provide multiple analytical functions, ranging from ranking energy related parameters to drilling into specific activities at variable spatio-temporal granularity for further insights on energy-related specificities of the energy performance. Screenshots from the different views of these two applications are presented in the Figure 4.

Following the demonstration of the customer applications and the long-term deployment of the different business strategies, the impact in terms of energy savings is depicted in the final results. The business stakeholders (retailers) should be provided with

tools in order to get quick insights about portfolio performance either at individual level or through groups that are linked to specific business campaigns.

By getting quick insights about customers performance, the business stakeholders can act accordingly and modify or reshape the different business models to be considered for their business (e.g. active participation of consumers in time shifting demand side management strategies is an indicator for promotion of time varying pricing schemas to their customers).

The focus in this section is to link the ICT-based energy management framework as presented in the previous section to the business context of the utilities. An in the loop approach has been considered for the analysis where the different business needs are transformed to business strategies and then to control models for the utilities and their customers. Through a trial and error process, the impact of the demonstration of the different tools can be very useful for the reconfiguration of the business planning of the utilities; very critical aspect in the deregulated and rapidly transforming energy market framework.

Figure 4: The behavioural based triggering framework and engine.

Figure 5: The Activity Clock Application view.

Figure 6: The business strategies performance monitoring viewpoint.

Figure 7: Pilot Buildings and installation of smart equipment.

Table 1: Impact Assessment – Energy Savings at demo sites.

	Residential	Commercial
Spain	-5.38%	-2.55%
Germany	-6.12%	-3.15%

3. Life validation and evaluation

The Holistic Energy Management framework as presented above is extensively validated in real-life conditions by a large and diverse population of residential and commercial consumers in five dispersed geographical areas (customers of energy retailers in Greece, France, Poland, Germany and Spain respectively) for a period of 18 months. Prior to any validation action, preparatory activities took place associated with

the installation of the equipment required for data gathering and further configuration and baseline calculations to meet retailer specific needs and requirements.

The equipment installation is a complex task and a key boundary for the mass penetration of real time building energy management systems. Heterogeneous device types spanning from smart meters, environmental sensors, HVAC controllers, smart dimmers and lamps were installed in

premises in order to ensure connectivity and control of energy savvy devices. The lack of standardization in the field of home automation is a key bottleneck and thus a case by case analysis and further deployment is required. Following equipment installation and system deployment, baseline activities are performed focusing on benchmarking and Energy Waste determination Layer. An innovative benchmark analysis is performed taking into account socio-demographic characteristics (geographical location & climate conditions, occupancy density, lifestyle issues, etc.) as well as energy related building characteristics (age, size, appliances, energy data, etc.) to apply well proven normalization methodologies (drawn mainly from Building Energy Rating as well as Operational Rating standardized methodologies) on the way to extract accurate baselines. Benchmarking is a critical preliminary step on the way to determine energy wastes and further design the appropriate energy efficiency guidance and strategies.

Following system deployment and baselining, the pilot evaluation aims to perform an overall analysis and evaluation of the operation phase divided into three sections: (i) technical evaluation, and adoption of the ICT solution (ii) user engagement of the different focus groups towards energy efficiency, and (iii) business evaluation and overall economic performance. The focus of the preliminary evaluation analysis is on the two latter points.

From the point of view of the portfolio energy performance, major energy consumption differences are observed between the groups in which the portfolios have been segmented. Moreover, it is also interesting to mention that significant differences between countries are evident given not only their climate conditions, but also their energy consumption (also implying energy generation, and thus GHG emissions). Such differences can be a result of multiple factors including the environmental awareness per country, the energy consumption habits of the inhabitants and the climate conditions etc. The impact of the preliminary evaluation at two demo sites for a short period of time (01/07/2020 – 20/09/2020) is presented in Table 1 (per building type).

Overall, the percentage reduction of consumption is not that high, mainly due to the phase of the project and the early phase of validation. In addition, we can point out that the consumption is much higher for residential users mainly due to their interest for their consumption and further mainly due to the activation of campaigns with focus on residential customers. Parameters as the synthesis of the users, the timeframe for evaluation and the level of engagement of the users should be thoroughly considered in the next phase.

The impact assessment results reported in this version are not the final as still pending the deployment and evaluation of the full set of services and business applications to the different demo sites. Moreover, due to COVID-19 restrictions, insights will be extracted from the data in order to show the impact of the new situation in the energy field. Some indicative results are presented in Figure 8.

The analysis is performed in the Spanish demo side for the period (1/2/2020 -30/6/2020). The data presented reflect a selection of 30 residential and 4 commercial buildings while for activity related analysis, data from 3 users have been selected for visualization.

As it is evident from the analysis, there is an increase of the consumption at residential level with a subsequent decrease of consumption at commercial buildings. In addition, impact is derived at the different activities considered in the project; focusing on the residential activities performed in premises.

4. Business Models Validation

With regards to the economic results, it is foreseen that the defined business models are cost-effective as it can be inferred from the results of the cost-benefit analysis performed at the different demo sites. A preliminary cost benefit analysis of the different business models defined in the project and the results are presented. In order to perform the analysis a user driven business modeling methodology was adopted

Figure 8: COVID-19 Impact (a) residential vs. commercial (b) cooking activity consumption.

Figure 9: A user driven business modeling methodology.

At first, the analysis of the market environment was performed in order to see the market dynamics to be considered for the synthesis of the country level business models. Following, collaboration with the business stakeholders is considered in order to extract the figures and the internal business parameters to be incorporated in the analysis. The market and business parameters are presented for the case of the Spanish Demo Site in Table 2.

Details about the penetration of services (BS-behavioural, AU- automation) at portfolio level, the impact potential, the consumption profile (RU-residential, CU-commercial), the pricing policy, the market conditions, the installation and software costs are considered in the analysis.

By having a clear understanding of the internal and external market environment, the profit/loss analysis is performed showing the economic impact for the Energy as a service framework examined in this paper. The results are provided for the case scenario considered for presentation in this section, focusing on revenues and costs, presented in the following table. The analysis covers both the customer side and the stakeholder side in order to ensure a win-win situation.

From a customer viewpoint, an on-average 7% reduction of electricity costs are considered through the penetration of the proposed framework. The analysis is performed for the utility side and for a 7-year business analysis, a positive IRR is reported, associated with a 65%

increase on the profit of the utility for the engagement in innovative business schemas.

We have to point out that a sensitivity analysis is required in order to properly quantify the business impact of the proposed framework under different market conditions. In the following table, the results of the sensitivity analysis for the Spanish case are presented.

The economic analysis complements the impact assessment analysis as reported in previous section. The demonstration and validation of the overall framework is in progress and the updated results will be available for further evaluation in the following months.

5. Conclusions

We presented a holistic energy management framework for utilities with focus on design of innovative applications and services for revealing, changing and re-freezing sustainable energy behaviour through accurate behavioural profiling, benchmarking, energy waste quantification and root cause definition, intelligent control, human-centric automation and energy performance certification. Along with the extensive technical description of the different applications, the validation activities performed in real life conditions are presented highlighting

Table 2: Business and Market parameters for business planning.

Cystomer Type	Energy Savings %		Energy consumption MWh/year	Energy costs €/kWh	Energy costs reduction due to load shift	Utility profit Energy €/MWh	Utility profit shifted €/MWh	Demand shifted %
	Behavioural	Automation						
Residential	12%	18%	3.6	0.2	0.1	10	9	25%
Commercial	12%	18%	49.56	0.15	0.1	10	9	25%
Cystomer Type	New clients %	Churn rate reduction %	Devices Costs		Installation costs		Software License	
			Behavioural	Automation	Behavioural	Automation	Behavioural	Automation
Residential	10%	5%	90 €	200 €	30 €	40 €	10.0 €	12 €
Commercial	0%	5%	500 €	1,000 €	90 €	200 €	10.0 €	12 €

Table 3: A win – win approach for customers and utilities.

	RU	CU	Discount rate
BS	5.33%	6.62%	7%
AU	8.00%	9.93%	55,493.87 €
			24%
			49.36%
			64.65%
			Increased Profit vs. Baseline

Table 4: Business Model evaluation – Sensitivity analysis.

Parameters	Discount Rate: 10%	ElecPrice Increase: 10%	CostsGoods Reduction : 15%	Savings Increase: 10%
NPV	27,219.57 €	97,840.52 €	81,644.20 €	111,798.26 €
ROI	24.05%	39.25%	37.54%	46.43%
IRR	39.66%	81.25%	73.17%	94.73%

the impact of the innovative framework in energy related key performance indicators.

From the business point of view, we complement the technical framework with first-of-a-kind business models for future-looking retailers interested to transform their business from commodity to energy services providers.

As a next step of the work, the detailed evaluation of the proposed framework will take place considering also user acceptance and engagement, behavioural change, energy

efficiency and overall ICT ecosystem performance, along with its cost-efficiency. On the other hand, the design of fine-grained applications on top of the existing ones will be considered on the way to provide a full suite of energy services aiming to address the new business needs and demands in the deregulated energy market environment. The upper aim is to ensure the scaling up and replication potential of the proposed energy management framework that will further ensure the marketization of the proposed framework in the current and future energy markets.

Acknowledgement

The work presented in this paper is co-funded by the EU HORIZON 2020 Programme (topic: “EE-07-2016-2017 - Behavioural change toward energy efficiency through ICT”) under grant agreement no. 768600 (project title: “UtilitEE - Utility Business Model Transformation through human-centric behavioural interventions and ICT tools for Energy Efficiency URL: <http://utilitee.eu/>).

Abbreviations

ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IPMVP	International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol
eDECs	Enhanced Display Energy Certificates
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
ESCO	Energy Service Company
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
VPPs	Virtual Power Plant
DSO	Distribution System Operator

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